

Paper 20

PRODUCTION CULTURE IN MICRO AND SMALL INDUSTRIES AND THE USE OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

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Abstract:

This article outlined the culture of manufacturing in micro and small sectors. Knowing the answers from the manufacturing culture gathered from 20 manufacturing sectors through study with 87 questionnaires. With the assistance of Agile manufacturing enablers, all the questionnaires prepared. The sample companies are customer-based manufacturers of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes. It has been observed from the study that micro-and small-scale sectors do not work with a single production methodology and no strategic method has been adopted. Most sectors face skilled labor shortages and market requirements shift. The main reason for this issue is bad data storage and reuse and bad adoption / non-adoption of the method of knowledge management in micro and small sectors.

Keywords: Agile Manufacturing, Data storage, Knowledge management

1. INTRODUCTION

The type of production and knowledge management back bone for its achievement in any of the sectors. When industrialization began, the manufacturing process began with craft manufacturing and when the industry became a big manufacturing process was moved to mass production scheme for craft manufacturing. However, mass production method provides a solution to satisfy big amounts but not quality. There, mass production system moved to lean manufacturing system for Japanese people to satisfy both the quality and low price by changing mass production system. However, this Lean production system is not good enough to satisfy the present vibrant market. Now the market for a day is completely dynamic in nature and this requires more and more item of variety as per client requirement. Lean or mass manufacturing is hard to meet the vibrant market requirements. There is a need to create one of the kind agile production systems[1] to react with quality product as soon as possible.

The manufacturing sectors are classified into three kinds based on employee numbers and

ceiling limits.

- Large scale
- Medium scale
- Small and micro scale

Here, the application of mass production, lean manufacturing and agile manufacturing[1] is quite simple for big and medium-sized sectors due to greater ceiling limits, which means that big and medium-sized companies can deal with vibrant markets by altering their production culture. But the vibrant market for micro and small-scale sectors is hard to deal with due to restricted resource and ceiling.

The research focused on small-scale and micro-industry production culture and how comparable to agile manufacturing ? The way of using technology, individuals, and organizational structure is crucial because it is the agile manufacturing's three main pillar. 2,3,4].

From the literature it is noted that, most of the small scale industries are used different type of tools/ philosophies to improve sustainability of the industries. There is no clarity about the manufacturing process in the industry and which manufacturing culturing is using, that is not sufficient for dynamic market. The manufacturing culture followed by the industries not mass production system or lean production system or flexible manufacturing system [5].

One manufacturing system was not followed by most sectors. It is quite hard to achieve dynamic client requirements with the present production system. Also, when the client requirement changes during the day, this leads to industry failure.

All small and micro-scale companies should change their present traditional manufacturing culture to one of the kind or agile manufacturing is essential to create profit in this vibrant requirement market situation. The way the techniques are integrated and used in the present production scheme is inappropriate [6,7,8]. It is most essential to follow the systematic manner in the manufacturing process in order to satisfy client requirements. In order to reach the market early, the sector should have adequate back-up data on the product and process, process standardization and concept of method and product development, it should reach all the company's staff with a minimum of time. Knowledge management is one of the most promising tools for small and micro-scale sectors to achieve their objective and market sustainability.[8,9] Computer and IT system application is crucial for effective knowledge management processes[10,11].

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research to know the production culture in small and micro industries, questionnaires were originally prepared based on agile enablers in manufacturing [1]. On the basis of technology, organisation and individuals, around 87 questions were prepared. Personal interview was discovered for all the responses to the questionnaires. Specifically, chosen manufacturing companies are ordered for this research to define manufacturing culture and industry agility. The gathered responses were transmitted to excel file after interviewing and that excel file was uploaded to Chronbach's SPSS statistical analysis instrument, the alpha questionnaire reliability check.

Figure1. Methodology

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Chronbach’s alpha reliability test

In this research a total of 87 questionnaires were used in small and micro-scale sectors to define manufacturing culture. All information including issues and responses uploaded to the SPSS statistical analysis instrument to verify the accuracy of questionnaires after completing the study of 20 sectors. The most common alpha method used by Chronbach was acquired from assessment to understand reliability and satisfactory outcome 0.836. Table 1 demonstrates the alpha outcomes of the Chronbach.

Table .1 Reliability statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.836	.877	86

Type of industries

Figure.2 Type of industries

The research is a manufacturer of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes based on client requirements for 20 small / micro sample companies. The private interview undertaken at managerial level and information uploaded to Google forms throughout this research. It took approximately 2-3 hours to finish the assignment. Fourteen small and six micro industries are taken as a sample in this study. For survey Likart scale is used 1- very low

- 2- low
- 3- medium/moderate
- 4- high
- 5- very high

Hierarchy in organization

Figure.3 Hierarchy in organization

In organisation, hierarchy is growing from flat to distinct levels. It is noted from the study that 75% of small and micro-scale sectors have no hierarchy in their organizational structure. Most sectors are running flat organizations. It implies that individuals with greater power also involve themselves in the process of manufacturing. But in the production or manufacturing process, people who are higher in authority can not be there in all the moment.

Organization structure

Figure.4 Organization structure

Of the 20 industries, the 10 industries have a moderate-level systematic organizational structure, 4 industries are good, followed by only one very good organizational structure. The five sectors have poor structure of organisation. Making organisation more and more effective is the appropriate arrangement of equipment, individuals and equipment.

Level of formal communication

Figure.5 Level of formal communication

The official communication scheme for sustainability is the backbone of any sector. By study, 17 sectors follow very bad formal communication and this type of communication is literally casual communication. Informal communication is cost-effective and helpful in fast coverage, but informal communication will not assist for long-term sustainability. For this it is necessary to have official communication with information recording scheme.

Level of employee transfer

Figure.6 Employee transferability

Worker transfer rate for other jobs in sector is nearly 60%. Transfer and communication process of employees in interconnected activity. The method of transferring employees or rotating jobs is a good practice of creating multi-skill workers. But while the employee should be updated for each employee whenever associated information / knowledge is transferred, this may improve the manufacturing lead time.

Level of group decision making

Figure.7 Level of group decision making

The study demonstrates that around 50% of sectors are very poor in group decision-making processes and 25% in mild stage and only 25% of sectors are prepared to adopt group decision-making. The habit of group decision making is interlinked with the transfer of employees and the management of information.

Achievement of productivity

Figure.8 Achievement of productivity

In order to enhance productivity, approximately 55 percent of sectors are not given any significance to information sharing culture. Only when using the method of knowledge management can any industry enhance its productivity.

Level of willingness to share knowledge

Figure.9 Level of willingness to share knowledge

According to study, 30 percent of staff in sectors are prepared to share their understanding at a moderate level and about 60 percent of staff are prepared to share knowledge above a mild level and only 10 percent are prepared to share expertise in sectors. The desire does not imply sharing the worker's understanding.

Level of infrastructure to promote knowledge share

Figure.10 Level of infrastructure to promote knowledge share

Every sector must provide the right infrastructure for information sharing. If the sharing of knowledge is done informally, it is considered a waste of time and resources. Once a skilled worker leaves his job then it is very difficult to train a fresh employee. Data and information stored in this moment will help to train the employee as soon as possible. It is noted that 95% of sectors do not provide any facilities for information sharing within the organisation.

Level of formal communication

Figure. 11. Level of formal communication

For efficient knowledge management sectors, formal communication must be followed and any process of knowledge sharing should be registered and stored. By doing so, the same can be achieved for training freshly joined staff.

Level of maintenance of previous data

Figure.12. Level of maintenance of previous data

The old / previous information or designs help us most in the manufacture of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes depending on client requirements to reach the market very soon or to respond quickly to client requirements.

Knowledge transfer through wall poster

Figure.13. Knowledge transfer through wall poster

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ufficient product-related data should be given for workspace. Information about the item makes it simple to do work in the manufacturing house. Survey claims no industry posts any data linked to the product in walls. This again leads to the manufacturing process being slowed down.

Level of knowledge transfer through hand book

Figure.14 Level of knowledge transfer through hand book

Providing adequate handbooks with identical product information facilitates job when staff receive the same item of distinct sizes each day. It's very hard to remember the distinct size aspect.

Level of Knowledge transfer through training

Figure.15 Level of Knowledge transfer through training

The worker knowledge can enhance by giving proper training to update their skills. Around 80% of industries are not organizing any training program for their employees. This may leads down skilling of the employees year by year.

Level of technology used

Figure. 16 Level of technology used

Worker knowledge can be enhanced to update their abilities by providing adequate training. Approximately 80 percent of sectors do not organize their workers ' training programmes. This can lead to the workers ' skills down year after year.

Data storage

Figure.17 Data storage

In the future manufacturing phase, data storage enables a lot. But 80-90% of the sectors do not store any information or full manufacturing process information. This type of habit makes the manufacturing process work double. If any comparable information are accessible then the information can be modified and reused with minimal price for fresh manufacturing method. Use of computer

Figure.18 Use of computer

It is essential to use computers in manufacturing processes efficiently and cost-effectively. The computer assists in multiple ways in the manufacturing process. Production details, design, modeling, and other work information can be stored in a computer and computer-based preparation. When repeated order is obtained, this type of work behavior decreases a lot of job burden. But study shows that about 90% of sectors do not use computer technology in

manufacturing processes. This leads to the vibrant market failing to respond rapidly.

Reuse of data

Figure.19 Reuse of data

Reuse of product information facilitates the process of product growth. That only 20 percent of sectors that reuse prior information in the manufacturing process are noted from study. Thirty-five percent of sectors partly affected by information reuse. 45 percent of the remaining sectors do not reuse any information. This leads to industry failure when they produce the same item of distinct sizes.

Repeated Order

Figure.20 Level of repeated order

Approximately 45 percent of sectors are in repeated order, and 45 percent of sectors are in

moderate order. Only 10 percent of sectors do not receive repeated order or very minimal order. This statistics suggests that a decent number of repeated orders are being received by most sectors.

Level of constant updating knowledge

Figure 21. Level of constant updating knowledge

The competitive company climate of today is very vibrant. The market is a sort driven by the client. The item should be manufactured in accordance with their requirement supplier and the lead time should also be much less. The product should be reached with the customer within a short period of time. In this situation, it is very critical to constantly update employee understanding. If employees are not great in the generation of ideas and poor in understanding of job then the reason for bad results will be. Only 15 percent of sectors confronting this competitive climate by updating understanding, 40 percent of sectors partly doing this, and about 45 percent of sectors have failed to do so.

Level of skilled labor problem

Figure.22 Level of skilled labour problem

Small-scale industries real issue is skilled labor. The issue of qualified labor is faced by 100% of sectors at distinct rates. The moderate level of the 40 percent of sectors facing labor problem, the high level of 40 percent and the very low level of 20 percent..

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is observed from the literature and survey of 20 manufacturing sectors that no small or micro-scale companies follow the same manufacturing technology and most companies are still following old traditional manufacturing culture and there is no integration between people technology and organisation. Each of these will play its part separately, and due to fewer individuals, most sectors will have a flat organizational framework. Because of bad faith in new technology and absence of understanding, the sectors were unable to take benefit of the flat organization structure. There is no adequate median / methodology for transferring understanding between the employee and management, resulting in industry failure or reduced effectiveness. There is plenty of scope for knowledge management application to effectively and efficiently integrate technology individuals and organisation. Those industries are still running with order technology they should follow knowledge management tool to improve agility with the help of computer system. By doing so, agility can be achieved. To gain agility or quick response to the dynamic market equal importance should given to people, technology and organization structure.

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